

Research Article

Structural Integrity Auditing of Large Oncological Datasets Through Demographic and Incidence Benchmark Validation

Marco Rocchetti

Department of Computer Science and Engineering

University of Bologna

Mura A. Zamboni 7, 40126 Bologna, Italy

Tel. +39 3920271318

Corresponding author: MR (marco.rocchetti@unibo.it)

ORCID: 0000-0003-1264-8595

Abstract

Large-scale observational datasets are increasingly used in oncological and public health research because of their statistical power and broad population coverage. However, dataset scale alone does not guarantee structural representativeness or epidemiological integrity. This study introduces a quantitative framework for auditing the structural consistency of large oncological cohorts through direct comparison with national benchmark statistics. The framework evaluates demographic representativeness across age strata, alignment of crude cancer incidence rates with official registries, and internal consistency within control-group subpopulations. The methodology was applied to a large national cohort study investigating cancer incidence in relation to COVID-19 vaccination status. Aggregated cohort metrics were compared against official 2022 national cancer registry benchmarks

and demographic statistics for the nation of interest, using quantitative indicators based on incidence rates, demographic deficits, and stratum-specific discrepancies. The analysis identified a multi-level structural divergence between the cohort and the national benchmark population. The cohort exhibited an overall cancer incidence deficit of 26.0% relative to official national statistics. The elderly population (≥ 65 years), representing the highest-risk oncological stratum, was underrepresented by 32.5% compared with the national demographic architecture. In addition, the unvaccinated elderly subgroup displayed a 45.1% lower crude cancer incidence than expected based on age-matched national reference data. These findings indicate substantial baseline discrepancies capable of influencing comparative epidemiological estimates within observational cohorts. This work does not investigate causal mechanisms and does not challenge the statistical associations originally reported in the analyzed study. Rather, it proposes a structural validation framework designed to assess the external consistency of large healthcare datasets before epidemiological associations are interpreted or generalized.

Keywords: Big data oncology; Cancer incidence metrics; Selection bias; External validity; Observational large size cohorts.

Highlights:

- A quantitative framework was developed to audit the structural integrity of large oncological datasets.
- Cohort metrics were validated through direct comparison with national demographic and cancer registry benchmarks.
- The analyzed cohort showed a 26.0% lower overall cancer incidence than official national statistics.
- The elderly population (≥ 65 years) was underrepresented by 32.5% relative to the national demographic structure.
- The unvaccinated elderly subgroup exhibited a 45.1% lower cancer incidence than expected from age-matched national reference data.

1. Introduction

The safety profile of COVID-19 vaccination has increasingly been addressed as a multifaceted biomedical challenge, characterized by a plurality of potential adverse events. Despite extensive research, the scientific debate remains significantly open, with contrasting findings that sustain a complex and ongoing international discussion on the subject [1].

In this context, recent observational research has utilized large-scale health administrative databases to investigate potential correlations between COVID-19 vaccination and the incidence of several diseases, including various forms of cancer. One study based on a massive (3 million individuals) administrative dataset, referenced as [2], suggests a higher rate of new cancer cases among the vaccinated population compared to the unvaccinated in an Asia-Pacific nation. While the magnitude of such datasets often implies a high degree of statistical power, the interpretability of the resulting associations could be put in comparison with established health benchmarks of the nation of interest for a better comprehension and utilization of the resulting findings.

Drawing on previous preliminary studies [3], the objective of this analysis is to verify the external consistency of the data extracted from a massive medical dataset like that referenced in [2] by comparing the cohort's metrics against official national statistics from gold-standard benchmarks, specifically regarding crude incidence rates and demographic distributions.

This analysis aims to quantify the extent to which those massive medical datasets reflect the oncological and demographic reality of the national population of interest, and whether potential discrepancies could influence the reported associations.

To conclude, it is worth reiterating that this is not a causal epidemiological analysis and not an inferential population study; it is a structural consistency audit of aggregated cohort metrics against national benchmark architectures.

2. Materials and Methods

A retrospective, cohort-based observational analysis centred on 2022 and drawing data from a N-size database [2] suggested a higher rate of new cancer cases among the COVID-19 vaccinated population compared to the unvaccinated. Raw data for estimating the incidence metrics were extracted from Table S4 of the Supplementary Material of the aforementioned study.

The original analysis started with an initial cohort of 8,407,849 individuals. Following a 1:4 Propensity Score Matching (PSM) [4], the final study population consisted of 2,975,035 individuals

(595,007 unvaccinated and 2,380,028 vaccinated), representing approximately 5.7% of the total Asian population of interest (51.7 million). The total number of cancer cases reported during the observation period was 12,133.

To evaluate the external consistency of the dataset, official 2022 statistics extracted from the Central Cancer Registries of the Asia-Pacific nation of interest were utilized as the definitive gold standard as reported in the following references [5-9].

Table 1 contrasts these national benchmarks with the specific metrics reported in [2].

Table 1. Structural Comparison: National Benchmarks vs. Massive Dataset

Category	Demographic Weight (<i>w</i>)	Participants (<i>N</i>)	Cancer Cases (<i>n</i>)	Crude Incidence Rate (per 10,000)
National (Gold Standard 2022)				
Elderly (≥ 65)	18.00%	N/A	N/A	155.20
Young (< 65)	82.00%	N/A	N/A	33.03
National Total	100.00%	N/A	N/A	55.02
Data from [2] (Unvaccinated)				
Elderly (≥ 65)	12.15%	72,285	616	85.22
Young (< 65)	87.85%	522,722	1,373	26.27

Total Unvaccinated	100.00%	595,007	1,989	33.43
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**Data from [2]
(Vaccinated)**

Elderly (≥ 65)	12.15%	289,140	3,283	113.54
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Young (< 65)	87.85%	2,090,888	6,861	32.81
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Total Vaccinated	100.00%	2,380,028	10,144	42.63
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To compare the cohort of [2] with the population of interest, three fundamental epidemiological formulas were utilized, also considering that the demographic homogeneity of the study population within a single national context renders the use of person-time adjustments or similar initiatives unnecessary for the stability of the incidence rates.

First, the Crude Cancer Incidence Rate (CR) was used. It determines the raw frequency of cancer cases within a specific group, normalized per 10,000 individuals to allow for direct comparison between different sample sizes:

$$CR = (Number\ of\ Cases / Population\ at\ Risk) \times 10,000 \quad (1).$$

Second, we used the Relative Demographic Deficit/Surplus (%). It measures the percentage deviation of the cohort's age distribution from the official national demographic architecture:

$$Relative\ Deficit\ \% = ((Population\ \% - Cohort\ \%) / Population\ \%) \times 100 \quad (2).$$

Third and final, the Difference in Incidence (% Suppression) was adopted. It quantifies the gap between the observed incidence rate in the study and the expected national reference rate:

$$\text{Difference \%} = ((\text{Reference CR} - \text{Cohort CR}) / \text{Reference CR}) \times 100 \quad (3).$$

As to the employed methodologies, it is needed to anticipate what follows.

First, given the auditing nature of this study, Confidence intervals (CIs) were not central to the present analysis, as this framework does not draw probabilistic inferences from a sample to generalize to an unknown universe; rather, it directly quantifies the absolute, macro-structural differences between the explicit census-scale metrics of the scrutinized cohort and the national cancer registry gold standard.

Second, as already indicated, age-standardization or person-time adjustments of the incidence rates are scientifically unnecessary, given that both the massive cohort under analysis and the reference benchmarks belong to the exact same national population and demographic architecture within the same calendar year, rendering crude rates directly comparable and epidemiologically stable.

Third, formal hypothesis testing is not mandatory here, because it is not tested any random sampling fluctuation or stochastic noise, but rather verified the existence of possible selection bias which cannot be statistically administered by significance testing.

Fourth, the quantitative methods exposed in this audit do not imply or investigate any mechanism of causality, since both the original study [2] and the present structural audit exclusively present and discuss the validity of statistical associations; this framework is strictly limited to verifying whether the baseline demographic and incidence integrity of the control group is reliable enough to sustain the external validity of the associations reported in the original study.

Finally, a granular validation of the oncological patients' vaccination status within the specific tumor strata remains structurally impossible, as such verified classification would strictly require direct access to the restricted individual-level primary datasets rather than aggregated summaries.

3. Results

We developed calculations to compute respectively: the total incidence, the demographic distribution and the group-specific incidence achieving the following results.

Applying Formula 1 to the cohort of [2] (12,133 cases / 2,975,035 participants) yields a Raw Incidence Rate of 40.78 per 10,000. The difference compared to the national benchmark (55.02) is calculated using Formula 3 as follows:

$$\text{Difference I} = ((40.78 - 55.02) / 55.02) \times 100 = -26.0\%.$$

In essence, the cohort from [2] exhibits a 26% lower overall incidence compared to national figures.

Then, we took into account the elderly population (≥ 65) which represents 12.15% of the original cohort (361,425 / 2,975,035). Applying Formula 2 to compare this with the national weight of 18.00% we get:

$$\text{Difference II} = ((12.15\% - 18.00\%) / 18.00\%) \times 100 = -32.5\%.$$

Clearly, the scrutinized cohort contains 32.5% fewer elderly individuals than the national reference population.

Finally, we focused on the unvaccinated elderly subgroup (Unvaccinated ≥ 65): the reported CR is 85.22 (616 cases / 72,285 participants). Applying Formula 3 against the national benchmark (155.20) for this specific stratum we got:

$$\text{Difference III} = ((85.22 - 155.20) / 155.20) \times 100 = -45.1\%$$

This puts in evidence that the unvaccinated elderly group in the cohort based on [2] presents 45.1% fewer cancer cases than expected based on national statistics.

4. Discussion

The evidence we have provided through the results from Formulas 1-3 suggest a three-level structural divergence cohort-population. Specifically, data extracted from the original massive dataset

is characterized by a -26.0% overall incidence gap, a -32.5% demographic under-representation of the high-risk elderly group, and a -45.1% divergence in the unvaccinated control group's incidence.

Based on these results, the associations vaccine/cancer reported stemming from the data of [2] should be carefully reconsidered in view of a possible selection bias. The observed increase in relative cancer risk could be a result stemming from a structurally unstable control group with a significantly suppressed baseline [10].

From a methodological perspective, it is critical to distinguish between internal and external validity.

Whether the mathematical modeling within the cohort, such as the already mentioned Propensity Score Matching or Cox proportional hazards [4], achieved strict internal validity by balancing specific internal covariates is an independent matter.

However, as explicitly mandated by Item 21 of the international STROBE (Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology) guidelines, a study must discuss the external validity (generalizability) of its findings [11]. A baseline control arm displaying a 45.1% systematic deficit in cancer cases relative to the national gold standard provide indication toward a structural detachment from the real-world population. Consequently, an unrepresentative baseline cohort may compromise its external validity and cannot be mathematically adjusted by internal balancing algorithms.

Standard epidemiological textbooks state that if significant selection biases affect a study, the resulting associations can be rightfully suspected of being non-generalizable [12]. Regardless of whether these associations are ultimately proven non-generalizable, they certainly cannot be considered immediately representative of the broader national population without further investigation with person-level detailed data.

5. Conclusion

The comparative analysis presented in this study highlights structural discrepancies between the cohort metrics from data of [2] and the official gold-standard national benchmarks, specifically the -26.0% overall incidence gap, the -32.5% demographic under-representation of the elderly, and the -45.1% case suppression in the unvaccinated control group.

Even if this could raise concerns about the presence of a selection bias, and standard epidemiological principles indicate that when a study is affected by relevant selection biases the resulting associations may be rightfully suspected of being non-generalizable, no one intends to diminish the relevance of the original investigations based on [2]. This is because we believe it should still be subject to further

investigation and because an access to the primary database required would be necessary to perform exhaustive counter-analyses.

Therefore, until proven otherwise, we are not disputing the statistical association found based on the original data, which correlates COVID-19 vaccination with a higher number of new cancer cases compared to the non-vaccinated population. What we do want is to highlight the discrepancies arising from a comparison with national benchmarks and medical data extracted from a very massive and influential dataset.

A solution to this methodological dilemma would be necessary to ensure scientific integrity and public trust. Such databases should be made public and accessible to the independent research community. Only through open access can researchers carry out in-depth, transparent analyses from every possible perspective to confirm or question relevant associations.

In closing, the discrepancies between the cohort data and national benchmark data we have observed highlight the importance of validating data extracted from large-scale medical datasets against established benchmarks, such as population-based disease incidence. Lack of similar controls are well documented in the literature as possible sources of distortion in observational studies. However, in the absence of access to individual-level data, it is not possible to assess whether, and to what extent, these discrepancies may influence the reported associations. For this reason, access to the primary data is always necessary to enable independent and conclusive verification.

For the completeness of this scientific record, it is worth reminding that similar questionable associations between COVID-19 vaccinations and other SAEs (Serious Adverse Effects) drawn by datasets similar to that scrutinized in this note were discussed in recently published studies by the same author of this article [13-14].

Conflicts of Interests

The Author declares no financial or non-financial support to this study.

Authors' Contributions: M.R. is the sole author of this work. He conceived the study, developed the mathematical framework, performed the statistical analysis, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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AI Disclosure

The Author declares no use of AI.

Data Availability Statement: All the data supporting the findings of this study are available from the referenced papers [5-9] and from the direct links to all the following datasets: a) World Bank. Population ages 65 and above (<https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.65UP.TO.ZS?locations=KR.>); b) Statista: Cancer crude incidence rate by age, 2022 ([https://www.statista.com/statistics/1440818/south-korea-cancer-crude-incidence-rate-by-age/.](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1440818/south-korea-cancer-crude-incidence-rate-by-age/)) and c) Supplementary Material III, Table S4 (https://static-content.springer.com/esm/art%3A10.1186%2Fs40364-025-00831-w/MediaObjects/40364_2025_831_MOESM3_ESM.docx)

Ethical Declarations

No humans, animals and private data are involved in this study, therefore ethical permission is not required.

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